

Open Science Guide

Advancing Open Science: Development of RPO's Open Science Strategy

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Executive Summary

The European research landscape prioritises scientific and technological leadership, driven by excellence, talent, and supportive conditions to facilitate research discoveries and innovation. Key to this is the [free movement](#) of researchers, knowledge, and technology, ensuring European competitiveness. The European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)) and the [EOSC Federation](#) are expected to play a central role in advancing Open Science. These initiatives enable researchers and innovators to access and share a vast array of open, reusable, and interoperable scientific publications, data, software, tools, and services. The strategy is also informed and aligned with the broader European research policy frameworks, such as the European Research Area (ERA) [Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#) and the European Commission's [Proposal for ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027](#) that set key actions to strengthen Europe's research ecosystem, emphasising Open Science and EOSC particularly, knowledge circulation, and the development of a digital research infrastructure that supports collaboration and innovation across borders.

In this context, this Guide aims to support the Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) to foster a sustainable and inclusive Open Science ecosystem within their institutions, aligning with the European Commission's broader objectives for research excellence, innovation, and collaboration. It is designed as a practical tool and a resource for decision-makers to develop and implement Open Science strategy within their institutions adapted to different institutional contexts.

The structured yet flexible approach allows RPOs to align their strategies with internal priorities and the broader Open Science landscape. The key steps include:

Assessment of Current State – Conducting a comprehensive review of the institution's research priorities, existing Open Science practices, infrastructure, policies, and stakeholder engagement. Benchmarking against national and international Open Science strategies.

Vision and Objectives – Establishing a clear vision statement that reflects institutional commitment to Open Science. Identifying key objectives and measurable outcomes to guide strategy implementation.

Stakeholders Engagement, Roles and Responsibilities – Securing buy-in from researchers, administrative staff, and leadership. Defining responsibilities within governance structures, including advisory boards, working groups, and implementation committees.

Priorities and Action Areas – Defining the most critical aspects of Open Science for the institution (e.g., Open Access, FAIR principles, citizen science, research assessment). Prioritise actions that align with institutional strengths and strategic goals.

Policies Develop and Implementation Framework – Establishing guidelines, governance mechanisms, and compliance measures to integrate Open Science principles into institutional workflows, ensuring alignment with national and European policies.

Resources Allocation and Capacity Building – Investing in necessary infrastructure, training, and support systems to enable effective adoption of Open Science practices.

Monitor, Evaluate, and Adapt – Define key performance indicators (KPIs) and feedback mechanisms to track progress, address challenges, and refine the strategy based on evolving research needs and Open Science developments.

This iterative, dynamic, and adaptable process recognises diversity of institutional structures, and encourages RPOs to adapt the OS strategy to their organisational culture and goals while ensuring coherence with global Open Science trends, including UNESCO guidelines and EOSC developments and in alignment with the objectives of the European Research Area.

Introduction

This guide is designed to support the leadership of research-performing organisations (RPOs) in designing and implementing a comprehensive Open Science (OS) strategy. It provides a flexible framework for reflecting on key aspects and processes that institutions should consider when planning and developing their Open Science strategies. By ensuring adaptability to various institutional contexts, the guide enables institutions to align their strategies with both internal priorities and the broader external Open Science ecosystem.

The process outlined in this guide is not a rigid chronological sequence but rather an iterative, dynamic, and adaptable approach. RPOs are encouraged to tailor the steps to fit their unique organisational cultures, structures, and goals while maintaining alignment with evolving global Open Science trends, including those driven by UNESCO and the European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)). This strategy development process is also informed and aligned with broader European research policy frameworks, such as the European Research Area (ERA) [Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#) and the European Commission's [Proposal for ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027](#) that set key actions to strengthen Europe's research ecosystem, emphasising Open Science and EOSC particularly, knowledge circulation, and the development of a digital research infrastructure that supports collaboration and innovation across borders.

The European focus on scientific and technological leadership driven by excellence, talent, and favourable conditions is necessary for advancing research discoveries and innovation. This includes free movement of researchers, knowledge, and technology to enable [competitiveness](#). In this context, the EOSC and the [EOSC EU Node](#), the European Commission's critical [milestone](#), aim to create a collaborative environment across Europe that accelerates research discoveries, enhances data-driven innovation and supports scientific progress. This allows researchers and innovators to find, access, and share tens of millions of open¹, reusable, and interoperable scientific publications, data, software, tools, and collaborative services - aligned with the [FAIR](#) principles² - fostering innovation across Europe's scientific landscape at every stage of the research lifecycle.

What is an Open Science Strategy?

Open Science is a multifaceted concept that transcends linguistic boundaries, driven by FAIR principles and practices that enhance the uptake of scientific knowledge by researchers, policymakers, industry and society. It propels a transition towards a more open, inclusive, and collaborative approach to conducting, evaluating, and disseminating research.

An Open Science strategy is a structured framework that articulates the RPO's overarching vision and goals for advancing Open Science practices within their institution. It translates broad

¹ The "A" of FAIR - [as open as possible, as restricted as necessary](#)

² Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable ([FAIR](#))

institutional goals into actionable and measurable steps, bridging the gap between long-term visions and specific actions.

The strategy may find its support in the national context. European countries follow varied approaches to forming the national strategies, roadmaps or guidelines for institutions in their countries. Invariably, these attempt to map the [European](#) and [global](#) context into the national space. Examples are many and varied. The RPOs are advised to consult their national context, and in the absence of one to consult examples of national strategies and roadmap across the European space: [Spain](#), [France](#), [Denmark](#), [Sweden](#), or [Netherlands](#).

Open Science Strategy and RPO's Long-term Goals

The Open Science strategy should clearly connect to the institution's broader mission, vision, and long-term priorities. By linking OS to strategic goals such as societal impact, collaboration, and innovation, the strategy becomes a reasonable extrapolation of the university's overall goals. This alignment not only enhances its relevance, but it also reflects the external and internal context in which the university operates.

Understanding how the Open Science Strategy aligns with the long-term goals ensures that the strategic objectives are tailored to the RPO's specific needs, aligned with the institutional capacities, and responsive to the broader Open Science ecosystem.

Relation Between Strategy, Policy, and Other Implementing Documents

The strategy serves as a guiding framework, providing coherence, focus, and alignment across the institution. As different aspects of the Strategy for the institution are considered, it is possible to consult examples of the RPOs that have the Open Science Strategy and or Policy published. These include [Technical University Delft](#), [Leibniz Universität Hannover](#)³, [Universitat de Barcelona](#), [Berlin University Alliance](#), [Leibniz Association](#), [University of Rijeka](#), [Open Research Office Berlin](#), and [Universität Zürich](#).

The strategy is implemented through policies, guidelines, codes of conduct, and the Research Data Management Plan (RDMP) – essential components of the governance framework. They define the rules, guidelines, compliance requirements, and principles for the implementation of Open Science and FAIR principles within the institution. These implementing documents help put these values and principles into practice by identifying relevant actors, such as the rectorates, deans, councils, legal and ICT departments, support offices, ethical boards, libraries, student councils and others.

³ Available in German language

Why do RPOs Need an Open Science Strategy?

For research organisations, an Open Science strategy is a transformative tool. It provides a structured way to adapt to evolving research landscapes, meet compliance requirements, and maximise the value of research outputs. By embedding Open Science into institutional practices, organisations not only enhance their operational efficiency but also increase their impact and visibility.

Implementing a well-structured Open Science strategy brings numerous benefits to research organisations, enhancing efficiency, collaboration and impact. Key advantages include:

- Open Science strategy ensures streamlined processes for sharing and accessing data and resources, reducing duplication and allowing researchers to build on each other's work more effectively. This increases the institution's overall research output.
- By committing to Open Science practices through a strategic framework, institutions demonstrate leadership and accountability in fostering transparency and innovation. This can enhance their attractiveness to collaborators, funders, and prospective students.
- National and European funders increasingly require Open Science compliance as a condition for grants. A strategic approach ensures the institution is well-positioned to meet these requirements, improving chances of securing funding and ensuring high-quality project execution.
- Open Science strategies enable institutions to make research outputs more accessible to the public, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. This enhances the relevance and societal impact of research while fostering trust in science.
- Strategy and implementing documents make Open Science practices more accessible, shaping the overall research culture within the RPO and strengthening communication between institutions, researchers, funders, and policymakers, and the public.

Framework for Open Science Strategy Development

Development of an Open Science strategy is an iterative process encompassing three key phases: development, implementation, and monitoring/evaluation. The development of an Open Science strategy starts with an assessment of existing practices, policies, and cultural attitudes toward Open Science within the institution. The cycle ends with the strategy implementation, from its publication and outreach to monitoring and review, as illustrated in the Figure 1 below. Each phase in this cycle is interconnected, ensuring continuous improvement and adaptability to evolving institutional priorities and global Open Science practices.

Figure 1. Illustration: Key elements of the Open Science Strategy Framework © TU Wien

Developing Open Science Strategy

To start developing the strategy, the RPO's leadership needs to foster a sense of participation to secure buy-in, active involvement, and collaboration of its support staff and researchers. It is key to find a way to engage them in all phases of this process as partners, rather than merely mandating or soliciting their involvement.

Defining clear roles and responsibilities is essential to ensure the effective development and, later, the implementation of the Open Science strategy. To achieve this, the RPO should:

1. Develop a governance framework to oversee the development and implementation of the strategy. This should include advisory boards, implementation committees, working groups, and departmental representatives;
2. Establish a structure to ensure key stakeholders are involved in decision-making processes throughout all phases of development and implementation;

3. Identify and engage stakeholders early, including researchers at different career stages (both early-career and senior), administrators, students, and external partners. Identify and onboard Open Science champions from various research departments to drive cultural change at the grassroots level;
4. Use participatory methods (e.g., workshops, focus groups) to involve stakeholders in all phases, from defining objectives to strategy implementation. For instance, working groups can be set up to focus on thematic or task-specific objectives during the strategy development (e.g., FAIR data practices, Open Access policies);
5. Collaborate with researchers, IT, legal, and administrative departments to ensure they participate in all phases of the development and implementation.

Define Roles and Responsibilities of Key Stakeholders

Scope

A well-structured framework with clearly assigned roles fosters accountability, prevents overlaps or gaps in responsibility, and ensures smooth coordination among stakeholders. The key stakeholders' roles and responsibilities need to cover a wide span of concerns from strategic oversight, operational execution, to advocacy and internal and external engagement. Stakeholder involvement is critical throughout the entire process. It ensures the strategy reflects diverse perspectives, fosters ownership, and aligns with the practical realities of implementation.

Steps

1. Assign clear roles to each entity and individual, outlining their specific duties, scope of authority, and reporting lines. For example:
 - a. Advisory Board: provide strategic oversight and ensure alignment with institutional priorities;
 - b. Working Groups: to focus on thematic or task-specific objectives during the strategy development (e.g., FAIR data practices, Open Access policies);
 - c. Implementation Committee: manage operational aspects, monitor progress, and report to the advisory board;
 - d. Departmental Champions: act as liaisons to promote Open Science within their units and gather feedback;
 - e. Researchers: to provide expert inputs on recommendations and, later, feedback on usability and impact within their research workflows;
 - f. Support Staff: to provide expert inputs and feedback on alignment with RPO's research infrastructure and compliance with open access and data-sharing practices;
2. Ensure that all stakeholders understand their responsibilities on all phases of the strategy development and implementation, and how their roles fit into the broader strategy. Clearly

document and disseminate this information during the planning phases, and in the final strategy and/or implementing documents;

3. Define roles for external actors (e.g., funding agencies, Open Science organisations, policy makers) to strengthen partnerships, provide guidance, and align with external requirements or trends.

Tools (examples)

RACI Matrix, Role Mapping Workshops, Job Descriptions for key roles, Stakeholder Analysis, Governance Models, Communication tools (e.g., organisational charts, process diagrams), Stakeholder Analysis, Focus Groups, Collaborative internal platforms, Town Hall Meetings

Analyse Current State and Circumstance (State-of-Play)

Scope

To start working on the framework for developing the OS strategy, it is necessary to review the institution's research agenda and strategic imperatives within its internal and external context. This assessment identifies strengths, gaps, and opportunities and serves as a foundation for setting realistic goals that are tailored to the university's specific needs, evidence-based, and aligned with institutional capacities.

Steps

1. Review the organisation's strategic priorities and research goals in terms of the broader vision for the institution's OS strategy:
 - a. Examine the internal and external context. Internally, this implies scrutiny of existing capacities, infrastructures, and resources, and externally a consideration of funding opportunities, policy requirements, and stakeholder interests;
 - b. Define how Open Science will contribute to achieving institutional goals, such as societal impact, enhanced collaboration, or fostering innovation;
 - c. Reflect on how Open Science and its vision aligns with the institution's long-term vision and mission;
2. Review existing Open Science practices:
 - a. Identify current activities such as Open Access publishing, data sharing, FAIR data principles, and Citizen Science engagement;
 - b. Highlight successful case studies and key contributors within the institution;
3. Assess possible alignment with existing policies:
 - a. Review existing institutional policies related to Open Access, data management, intellectual property rights, and research ethics;

- b. Ensure alignment with national strategies, international standards (e.g., UNESCO [recommendations](#) on Open Science), and initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#));
4. Assess institutional culture:
 - a. Conduct surveys, interviews, or focus groups to gauge awareness, perceptions, and attitudes toward Open Science;
 - b. Identify barriers to adoption, such as limited incentives, knowledge gaps, or policy constraints;
5. Benchmark against peer institutions:
 - a. Compare your organisation's Open Science practices with leading national and international institutions and initiatives, best practices (e.g. [cOAlition S](#), [CoARA](#), [EOSC SRIA](#), [DORA](#)) that may be applicable to your organisation's context;
6. Identify gaps and opportunities:
 - a. Synthesise findings to pinpoint areas for improvement and growth;
 - b. Recognise potential for collaboration and innovation within the Open Science ecosystem.

Tools (examples)

Theory of Change, Stakeholder Mapping, Surveys, and Interviews, Focus Groups or Workshops, Gap, problem tree, SWOT, PESTLE, 5C, VRIO or Porter's Five Forces analysis, Benchmarking with National and International Institutions, Institutional policy review

Create Vision Statement, Set Key Objectives

Scope

The vision statement defines the organisation's aspirations for Open Science and serves as a guiding principle for the strategy. It should inspire stakeholders and reflect the institution's values, ambitions, and commitment to Open Science. Objectives translate the vision into specific, actionable goals. They provide direction for the strategy and establish clear targets to measure progress.

Steps

1. Draft a concise and compelling vision statement for Open Science at your university;
2. Ensure the vision statement reflects how the organisation contributes to and benefits from the broader Open Science ecosystem, including initiatives like:
 - a. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): Engage with EOSC principles, such as promoting FAIR data practices, federated infrastructures, and cross-border collaborations;

- b. National Open Science strategies: Align with country-specific policies and frameworks to ensure compliance and synergy;
 - c. Global standards: Acknowledge international trends in Open Science, such as UNESCO's Open Science recommendations;
3. Collaborate with stakeholders to refine and validate the vision;
 4. Ensure the vision aligns with the institution's overall mission and goals;
 5. Identify key objectives, aligned with the vision;
 6. Develop measurable metrics to track progress toward achieving objectives;
 7. Define both quantitative and qualitative indicators (both baseline and target to ensure a holistic approach to measurement).

Tools (examples)

Visioning Workshops, Consensus Building, Storytelling (User stories), SMART Goals, Benchmarking, OKRs (Objectives and Key Results)

Assess Expected Impact of Open Science

Scope

Articulating the benefits of Open Science ensures clarity about its value to researchers at different career stages, students, the institution, and society. Assessing and understanding its impact enables a well-informed, evidence-based strategy that highlights its advantages and addresses potential concerns.

Steps

1. Clearly define the benefits Open Science can bring to the institution and its stakeholders, including transparency, accessibility, and societal contributions;
2. Assess the institution's current Open Science practices and infrastructure, benchmarking against international frameworks, to guide strategic planning;
3. Evaluate the costs and benefits associated with Open Science practices;
4. Identify risks and challenges that may arise during implementation.

Tools (examples)

Scenario planning, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Case Studies, Bibliometric and Altmetric Analysis, Social and Economic Impact Assessment

Identify Priorities - Critical Areas of Open Science

Scope

Not all aspects of Open Science are equally critical for every institution. Identifying priority areas ensures the strategy focuses on practices that deliver the greatest value and align with institutional goals. Various aspects of Open Science (e.g., Open Access, FAIR data, Research Assessment, Citizen Science, Intellectual Property Rights) should be assessed to evaluate most relevant ones for the institution, considering its research focus, strategic priorities and resources. Next, the areas where practices are underdeveloped or where improvements would have the most impact can be prioritised based on their feasibility and importance to achieving the goals. The following steps present a list of possible actions that can be implemented for prioritised areas.

Steps

1. Form a dedicated Open Science committee or leadership team to oversee implementation, monitor progress, and ensure stakeholder participation and engagement;
2. Invest in- or join scalable, interoperable, and FAIR-compliant research data management (RDM) repositories while ensuring adequate staffing and researcher training to support participation in- or management of these systems. Define the institution's preferred Open Access model (e.g., Diamond, Green) and provide clear guidance, funding support, compliance mechanisms, and access points to journals, publishing and reproducibility guidelines for researchers;
3. Define preferred licensing options for research outputs (e.g., publications, datasets, and educational materials), mandatory scientific citation standards, licensing statement templates, and license URLs;
4. Define and encourage adoption and use of standardised, human- and machine-readable metadata with structured [semantic artifacts](#) that ensure findability, interoperability, and reuse of research data, findings, and publications;
5. Broaden [research assessment](#) framework beyond journal impact factors to include Open Science contributions such as dataset sharing, software, preprints, and public engagement; For details see this section on Incentives;
6. Implement reward mechanisms to recognise and encourage researchers and support staff's contributions to Open Science. These include career benefits, funding preferences, and institutional recognition programs to embrace and promote Open Science practices; See this section on Incentives for more information;
7. Provide targeted training to researchers and support staff on Open Science tools, FAIR data, and open publishing; (see [Training Chapter the Guide](#) for more information);
8. Provide clear guidelines to open the research process to citizens and enable public participation in all phases of research. Support and acknowledge community-led contributions and provide mechanisms for recognition of their efforts and contributions;

9. Support outreach and public engagement in research activities.

Tools (examples)

Gap Analysis or Priority Matrices, Stakeholder Mapping and Surveys, RACI analysis, Balanced Scorecards; consult FAIR [Principles](#), [EOSC Federation Handbook](#), OpenAIRE's RDM [Handbook](#), and RDA's [Principles](#)

Identify Key Resources

Scope

Implementation of an Open Science Strategy depends on extensive infrastructure investment, tools, and supporting services. These include the establishment and maintenance of institutional repositories, data management, and solutions that enable research data to be findable, accessible, and machine-actionable with robust access controls. Competent support staff are essential to provide research data management and publication services. Existing infrastructures and tools should be assessed for scalability and adaptability to meet the institution's long-term strategic objectives. A specialised team should oversee this process, ensuring the efficient use of internal and external resources.

Steps

1. Identify the resources required to implement each aspect of the Open Science strategy, including:
 - a. Human Resources: Staff, researchers, librarians, IT specialists, data stewards, and external advisors,
 - b. Infrastructure: Open Access repositories, FAIR-compliant data storage, digital tools, and collaboration platforms,
 - c. Financial Resources: Budget for infrastructure development, training programs, or hiring new personnel,
 - d. Training and Capacity Building: Knowledge and skill development programs for staff and researchers.
2. Conduct a thorough inventory of the institution's current resources to determine what is already available (existing publication or FAIR data repositories or data storage systems, personnel with relevant expertise, training programs or policies already in place);
3. Compare resource needs with existing resources to identify gaps. Determine what additional resources are essential to address these gaps effectively;
4. Identify resources that can be outsourced to external providers or organisations to reduce costs and leverage specialised expertise (i.e., outsourcing technical support for repository management, engaging external consultants or trainers for capacity building, collaborating with Open Science service providers for software or infrastructure needs);

5. Create a detailed plan to allocate resources effectively. Ensure the plan is tied to specific goals and objectives outlined in the strategy.

Tools (examples)

Resource Mapping, SWOT Analysis of Resources, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Benchmarking, Collaborative resource development (partnership with an external organisation), outsourcing framework

Ensure Competence Flexibility

Scope

For an Open Science strategy to succeed, the staff responsible for its implementation must have the appropriate competencies, skills, and knowledge to handle their roles effectively. Moreover, it is crucial to foster flexibility by enabling staff to adapt to new developments, update their expertise, and build networks. Competence flexibility ensures that the institution remains agile and responsive to the evolving landscape of Open Science, including advancements in technology, changing policies, and emerging best practices.

Steps

1. Evaluate the existing knowledge, skills, and expertise of the staff responsible for implementing the strategy. Identify gaps in competencies that could hinder successful execution;
2. Offer targeted training programs, workshops, and courses to ensure staff acquire the necessary skills for Open Science implementation. Focus areas may include FAIR data principles; Intellectual Property Rights; Open Access publishing; repository management; Legal and ethical aspects of Open Science, such as copyright and data privacy; domain-specific RDM training; Mentorship programs for early-career researchers and onboarding programs for new hires;
3. Create a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging staff to regularly update their skills and stay informed about Open Science trends and developments;
4. Facilitate opportunities for staff to engage with external Open Science networks, conferences, and communities. This helps them gain fresh perspectives, share knowledge, and build collaborations;
5. Design roles with flexibility so staff can adapt to changes in technology, policies, or institutional priorities. For example, allow staff to allocate time for learning or experimenting with new tools and methods;
6. Conduct periodic reviews to assess whether staff competencies remain aligned with the institution's evolving Open Science goals. Update training plans and resources as needed.

Tools (examples)

Competency Mapping, Learning Management Systems (LMS), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), internal learning platforms, peer learning and mentorship programs, Knowledge exchange with external organisations, workshops and conferences, flexible (individual) development plans, Job Rotations or Cross-Functional Teams, Open Life Science program

Finalise and Release Strategy

Scope

The Open Science Strategy needs to reflect inputs from all stages of development and be actionable, clear, and aligned with institutional goals. To bring the strategy to life, the RPO needs to translate strategic objectives into actions through implementing documents, such as policies, guidelines, codes of conduct, data governance framework, Research Data Management Plan (RDMP), or AI strategies. These documents contain responsibilities, resource utilisation plans, and deadlines to guide the institution through implementation of the principles of the strategy.

The implementation activities should also seek to encourage take-up and utilisation of the Open Science policy by academics and researchers and make such concepts part of their workaday activities and research. By prioritising the needs of the research community and providing the right support and resources, the institution can establish a sustainable means for Open Science to be applied and have lasting impacts.

Steps

1. Distribute draft strategies and implementing documents to stakeholders for review;
2. Incorporate stakeholder feedback into the final draft;
3. Define actionable plans with timelines, responsibilities, and resources;
4. Ensure the strategy and implementing documents are clearly communicated.

Tools (examples)

Iterative drafting (circulate drafts for review and refinement), Peer Reviews, Visualisation Tools

Implementing Open Science Strategy

Communicate Published Open Science Strategy

Scope

The effective communication of the Open Science strategy and its implementing documents is critical to ensure awareness, understanding, and engagement among stakeholders. A well-communicated strategy creates transparency, fosters institutional buy-in, and builds trust. It should target diverse audiences, including researchers, staff, students, and external stakeholders, ensuring they understand the strategy's goals, their roles, and the benefits of participation.

Steps

1. Define the key internal and external stakeholders who need to be informed about the strategy. These may include researchers, administrative staff, students, external partners, funders, and policymakers;
2. Create clear and relevant messaging that resonates with different stakeholders:
 - a. For Researchers: Emphasise incentives, career benefits, and support resources;
 - b. For Administrators: Highlight alignment with institutional goals and efficiency improvements;
 - c. For External Stakeholders: Showcase compliance with global standards and contributions to societal impact.
3. Use a mix of traditional and digital tools to disseminate the strategy (including university intranet, email newsletters, and press releases, dedicated Open Science webpages or microsites, workshops, webinars, and town hall meetings);
4. Create materials to explain the strategy in an accessible way, i.e., executive summaries, infographics, and videos; FAQs and guides explaining key components and roles.
5. Organize events, such as workshops or Q&A sessions, where stakeholders can learn about the strategy and clarify their roles;
6. Collect feedback on how well the strategy is understood and identify gaps in communication. Use this feedback to refine future messaging.

Tools (examples)

Infographics and visual summaries, stakeholder workshops, Digital Platforms (a dedicated web page or microsite for the Open Science strategy with downloadable resources, video tutorials, and updates), Multi-Language Support (translate key documents and materials), Leadership Advocacy, Newsletters

Incentivise for Uptake of Open Science Strategy

Scope

Encouraging researchers and support staff to adopt and actively engage with the Open Science strategy requires targeted incentives. These incentives can address cultural, practical, and systemic barriers to participation while emphasising the personal and professional benefits of Open Science. They should be aligned with institutional priorities and tailored to researchers' and support staff's needs, ensuring that Open Science practices are seen as rewarding, career-enhancing, and professionally valuable. Incentivising Open Science requires a comprehensive, multi-level approach, ensuring that researchers and support staff see tangible career benefits, funding opportunities, and institutional recognition. By leveraging frameworks such as [CoARA](#), [DORA](#), [EOSC](#), and UNESCO, institutions can foster a sustainable culture of Open Science adoption. Effective incentivisation fosters widespread adoption, drives long-term commitment, and embeds Open Science principles into the institution's culture.

Steps

1. Understand what motivates researchers to participate in Open Science. Analyse existing options for career advancement, funding opportunities (e.g., Horizon Europe), collaboration, or societal impact;
2. Ensure that Open Science practices (e.g., publishing in Open Access, sharing FAIR-compliant data and software) are recognised in hiring, promotion, and tenure evaluations;
3. Ensure that Open Science practices are formally recognised in hiring, promotions, tenure, and evaluations, including Open Access publishing and contributions to open repositories; sharing digital research products, software, and publications; participating in open peer reviews and citizen science initiatives;
4. Allocate resources to support researchers in adopting Open Science, such as grants, reduced publishing fees, or access to necessary infrastructure;
5. Establish systems to reward researchers for engaging in Open Science practices, including public acknowledgment, awards, or monetary bonuses;
6. Provide incentives and define reward mechanisms for the support staff, to recognise and reward their contributions and support they provide to researchers;
7. Provide workshops, professional support, mentorship, and learning opportunities to make it easier for researchers to transition to Open Science practices. For more information, please see the [Training Chapter of the Guide](#);
8. Create institutional policies that integrate incentivisation into the broader Open Science framework, ensuring that participation is systematically encouraged at every level. Integrate incentives into organisation's strategic plans.

Tools (examples)

Recognition & awards (Open Science awards, public and press showcasing of best practices, fellowships, institutional badges), Career advancement (Open Science contributions count towards promotion & tenure), financial incentives (Open Access publishing grants and funds, FAIR data management support), training & mentorship, networking (e.g., LERU and other institutional support for Open Science events, international collaborations)

Monitor Implementation, Evaluate, and Update Strategy

Scope

The Open Science strategy needs to be periodically checked to ascertain that it is working correctly and can continue to develop appropriately. It continually evolves to reflect new challenges, opportunities, and feedback. This includes setting key performance indicators (KPIs) to review progress at specific starting points, initial and mid-term reviews during usage period. These reviews check how well the strategy is working and provide useful feedback for refinement. Ongoing strategy revision keeps useful, effective, and aligned with new technology and policy developments.

Transparency in accountability is required for the monitoring process. Roles and responsibilities need to be well defined, giving supervision to specific individuals or committees within the institution. This ensures that progress is tracked on a regular basis, changes are made when needed, and stakeholders are updated on successes and areas of improvement. A transparent and flexible monitoring system, enable the institution to continually improve its Open Science initiatives.

Steps

1. Assign monitoring responsibilities to specific individuals or committees to ensure transparency and trackable oversight;
2. Establish a monitoring committee or task force to oversee progress, identify obstacles, and make recommendations. Regularly communicate findings to leadership and stakeholders;
3. Establish regular reporting mechanisms to review achievements;
4. Analyse key indicators defined earlier to track progress;
5. Periodically review and revise the strategy to maintain relevance;
6. Use feedback from stakeholders received during the revision process to refine implementation practices. Engaged stakeholders ensure continued alignment;
7. Adapt to developments in Open Science practices, technologies, or policies;
8. Track mandatory Open Science compliance for internal research funding;
9. Regular institutional reporting on Open Science adoption and progress.

Tools (examples)

KPI Dashboards, Progress Reports, Feedback (surveys or interviews), Lessons Learned, External Audits, continuous stakeholder engagement

Glossary

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
cOAlition S	An initiative launched in 2018 to accelerate Open Access publishing.	Supports Plan S, requiring publicly funded research to be published in Open Access journals or platforms.	Plan S implementation guidelines.
CC BY (Attribution)	A Creative Commons license allows reuse with credit to the original author.	Ensures authors are credited while enabling broad reuse of research outputs.	Researchers receive due credit for their work while maximizing its reach and impact.
CC0 (Public Domain Dedication)	A Creative Commons license allows works to be freely shared without restrictions.	Maximises reusability by removing all restrictions on use, allowing data to be freely available.	Zenodo dataset licensing.
Citizen Science	Citizen science is the involvement of the public in scientific research—from formulating questions and collecting data to interpreting results.	This collaborative approach has the potential to bridge the gap between science, policymakers, and society, leading to more impactful outcomes. It encourages public participation in data collection, analysis, and dissemination, strengthening science-society collaboration.	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), EU Citizen Science Platform, ECSA Guidelines, European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Guidelines, and EU Citizen Science Platform.
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment	A European-led initiative that fosters reforms in research assessment by promoting qualitative peer review, open science practices, and broader impact considerations beyond traditional citation-based metrics.	CoARA Agreement (2022).
Digital Transformation at HEI	A toolkit to support the development of digital strategies, assessment of digital maturity across the organisation and the creation of actionable roadmaps and plans for implementation.	Enhances teaching, research, and administrative processes through digital tools and infrastructures.	JISC Guide on Digital Transformation .
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment	A global initiative established in 2012 to promote fair and responsible research assessment, advocating for the reduced reliance on journal-based metrics like the Journal Impact Factor in evaluating research quality. Encourages diverse metrics and qualitative assessment for research impact.	DORA tools for fair research evaluation.

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)	A European initiative to provide a digital infrastructure for storing and sharing research data.	Supports researchers with tools, services, and data storage solutions to promote Open Science practices.	EOSC Federation Handbook , EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) , EOSC Skills4EOSC Program .
ERA	European Research Area	ERA enhances coordination of EU research efforts, boosting the circulation of researchers and knowledge, building critical mass, and promoting excellence.	The New European Research Area Platform Charting Progress in A New Era (PDF)
5C Analysis	A strategic tool analysing Company, Collaborators, Customers, Competitors, and Climate in Open Science.	Supports the development of Open Science initiatives by understanding key players and the research ecosystem.	Institutional Open Science initiatives.
FAIR	A framework ensuring research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.	Facilitates data sharing and long-term preservation to enhance research transparency and reproducibility.	GO FAIR Initiative, FAIRsFAIR Policy Recommendations (2021), The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Nature).
Future of Research Evaluation	A synthesis of current debates and developments in research evaluation (2023).	Examines trends, challenges, and new approaches in research assessment.	European Commission policy papers on research evaluation.
Gap Analysis	Assess and prioritise Open Science initiatives.	Identifies existing Open Science strengths and weaknesses.	
GitHub & GitLab	Online platforms for version control and collaborative software development.	Enable researchers to share, archive, and collaborate on code and software.	CERN Open-Source Software, GitHub-Zenodo integration.
Horizon Europe	The EU's flagship funding program for research and innovation.	Mandates Open Science practices for funding eligibility, ensuring public access to research outcomes.	Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2025
Incentives and Rewards	Rewards are the formal mechanisms used to acknowledge and recognise researchers for their open science efforts. They are typically provided by institutions, funders, or other organisations.	Create an environment that fosters open science, ultimately leading to more transparent, collaborative, and impactful research.	Recommendations on Open Science Rewards and Incentives .

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
League of European Research Universities (LERU)	A network of research-intensive universities that advocates for Open Science and offers institutional policy recommendations.	Provides guidance on implementing Open Science practices and influences EU policies related to research.	LERU Report on Implementing Open Science.
LMS	Learning Management System		
Licensing	Legal frameworks that define how research outputs (publications, datasets, and materials) can be used and shared.	Ensures appropriate attribution, accessibility, and reuse of research content.	Creative Commons Licenses (CC BY, CC0), Open Data Commons (ODC-BY, ODC-ODbL).
National Open Science Strategy	A framework that addresses Open Science values, principles, and practices to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone.	Ensures that national policies promote Open Science and align with international best practices.	National strategies in Spain , France , Nordic countries, Denmark, Netherlands.
ODC-BY (Attribution License)	A license under Open Data Commons that allows sharing and adaptation of datasets with attribution.	Enables data reuse while ensuring proper credit is given to the original creator.	ODC-BY license facilitates the wide dissemination and use of quality data, enabling it to benefit policy decisions, inform the public, and potentially drive the development of useful applications.
ODC-ODbL (Open Database License)	A license under Open Data Commons that requires derived works of databases to remain open.	Protects open data by ensuring any modified versions of the dataset are shared openly.	OpenAIRE Research Graph.
OER	Open Educational Resources		
Open Research	The practice of encouraging the use of open-source tools, shared code repositories, and reproducibility guidelines in scientific research.	Promotes collaboration and transparency by making research outputs, including software, datasets, and methodologies, freely accessible and reusable.	Software Heritage, Reproducibility Frameworks (Reproducibility Networks), GitHub, Zenodo.
OLS (Open Life Science Program)	A program supporting the Open Life Science community through training and mentoring to encourage open research practices.	Provides resources and support for researchers to adopt open science practices in their work.	OLS Training Program , open research initiatives.
Open Science Policy	A set of guidelines or frameworks for institutions to adopt Open Science practices.	Guides institutions on how to implement and promote Open Science principles.	OpenAIRE toolkit for policymakers.

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
Open Science Strategy	A guiding framework aimed at promoting open science globally. It recognises that open science is crucial for accelerating scientific progress, fostering innovation, and addressing global challenges. It's not a single document, but rather a set of principles, recommendations, and actions endorsed by UNESCO member states.	Helps guide institutions in their journey to fully adopt Open Science practices, including data sharing and open publishing.	National Open Science Strategy (ENCA) 2023-2027, Spain.
Open Science Roadmap	A detailed plan outlining the adoption and integration of Open Science practices at an institutional or national level.	Outlines specific steps and actions that UNESCO member states, research institutions, funders, and other stakeholders should take to implement the strategy's principles and achieve its goals.	LERU Open Science Roadmap, LIBER Roadmap for Open Science.
OpenAIRE	A key EU e-Infrastructure whose mission is to establish, maintain and operate an open and sustainable scholarly communication infrastructure and provide the necessary services, resources and network for supporting a common European e-science environment.	It supports a set of services to facilitate the road to Open Science.	OpenAIRE Training & Resources .
PESTLE Analysis	A framework analysing Political, Economical, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental factors affecting Open Science.	Helps assess external influences on Open Science adoption and long-term sustainability.	Evaluating Open Science policies in different geopolitical contexts.
Porter's Five Forces Analysis	A model for analysing the competitive environment of Open Science initiatives.	Provides a valuable framework for analysing the competitive landscape of open science and identifying strategies to promote its growth and impact.	Evaluating the impact of commercial publishers on Open Access.
Priority Matrices	Assess and prioritise Open Science initiatives.	Ranks Open Science areas by feasibility and impact.	
Problem Tree Analysis	A visual tool that maps causes and effects of challenges in Open Science.	Helps analyse barriers to Open Science and develop targeted interventions.	Identifying issues in Open Access implementation, e.g., lack of incentives, inadequate infrastructure.

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
RDA (Research Data Alliance)	An international organisation that promotes data sharing and management best practices.	Facilitates collaboration on global data sharing initiatives, ensuring data is properly managed and shared.	RDA Recommendations and Outputs.
RDM	Research Data Management	Cross-cutting and comprehensive process that reflects the entire data lifecycle.	Science Europe RDM RDM at TU Wien
RDMP	Research Data Management Plan	A formal document on research data management practices. It describes data acquisition, management, preservation, publishing, and sharing for research projects.	Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management
Reproducibility Networks	A consortium of open research working groups, often peer led.	The groups operate on a wheel-and-spoke model across a particular country, in which the network connects local cross-disciplinary researchers, groups, and institutions with a central steering group, who also connect with external stakeholders in the research ecosystem.	UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN), German Reproducibility Network, (RNDE).
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda	A general framework for future research, development and innovation activities. It is used to inform the work programmes via the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR).	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).
SWOT Analysis	A strategic tool for assessing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in Open Science initiatives.	Provides a structured approach to evaluating frameworks. A SWOT analysis is designed to facilitate a realistic, fact-based, data-driven look at the strengths and weaknesses of an organisation.	
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation	Promotes Open Science through policy development, guidelines, and tools to ensure equal access to scientific knowledge.	UNESCO Open Science Toolkit , Software Heritage Initiative .
VRIO Analysis	A method for evaluating the value, rarity, imitability, and organisation of Open Science resources.	Helps institutions to assess the value and impact of open science practices and resources. Answers questions like: Does Open Access to research publications increase the visibility and impact of research?	